

THE PROBLEM OF CORRECT TIME DISTRIBUTION AND ITS PSYCHOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

This article deals with the topic of correct time allocation. At the same time, the solutions of this problem are described with a psychological approach to the problem of correct distribution of time. The lives and careers of most successful people show that the key to success is time management. Successful business people invest their time in things that will provide them with new knowledge, creative decisions and energy in the future. At first, their success may not be noticeable. However, as a result of long-term investments, they reach unprecedented heights.

Key words

time, problem, motivation, effort, result, success.

INTRODUCTION:

The life experiences of many successful people show that the main key to success is the correct allocation of time. Successful business people know how to allocate and use their time. This will help them in the future to invest in new knowledge, creative decisions, things that will provide them with energy and, of course, high-profit projects. In the early years, their success may not be noticeable. However, as a result of long-term investments, they reach unprecedented heights. Research shows that managing your time effectively reduces stress and increases productivity and life satisfaction.

Don't complain about too much work and no time. Fear that there is too much time and no work. Idleness is what makes a person crazy.

People's writer of Uzbekistan O'tkir Hoshimov

MAIN PART:

Many people are sometimes so busy that they don't notice the events and happenings around them. Spending time on unnecessary activities is even worse. And the correct allocation of time creates the basis for conquering great heights in

the future. Successful people have useful habits that are worth emulating. Here are some effective tips to help you reap the benefits in the long run:

- Keeping a diary;
- Take a break;
- Walking at least 15 minutes a day;
- Read more books;
- Finding a good interlocutor;
- Not being afraid to experiment.

Keeping a diary. Writing down personal thoughts, plans, and events in life helps people become more mindful and perceptive. Thinking changes, worldview develops and learns to make the right decisions. Many successful people usually keep a personal diary. For example, John Adams, the second president of the United States, kept a diary throughout his life, and by the end of his life, the number of them reached 50. Albert Einstein left behind various manuscripts of more than 80,000 pages. Benjamin Franklin asked himself every morning, "What good thing should I do today?" And every evening, I start my day with the question "What did I do well today?" ended with a question. Steve Jobs stood in front of the mirror and asked, "If today were my last day, would I do the things I planned to do?" interested.

Take a break. Breaks during the day not only increase productivity, but also develop the potential for creative thinking. "An hour or an hour and a half of sleep to catch up will have the same impact on learning as eight hours of sleep," says sleep researcher Sarah Mednick.

Walk at least 15 minutes a day. According to scientists, if a student takes a one-hour break during the day and sleeps in the morning, they will do 30% better on control tests in the evening. This habit was typical of Albert Einstein, Thomas Edison, Winston Churchill, John F. Kennedy, Ronald Reagan, John Rockefeller and many other great people. For example, Leonardo da Vinci experimented with hemiphasic sleep, breaking sleep into multiple 10-minute chunks. Napoleon preferred to sleep before each battle. The famous actor Arnold Schwarzenegger takes a nap every day after lunch. Modern science confirms the benefits of this habit.

Successful people definitely make time for sports in their daily routine. Walking can also be great exercise. Charles Darwin walked twice a day: near noon and before sunset. Beethoven went for a long walk after lunch and carried a pen and paper with him in order to capture the inspiration on paper. Charles Dickens walked more than 10 kilometers a day, which helped him not to get bored by

burying himself in work. Steve Jobs used to go for a walk while preparing for an important meeting. This habit must be mastered. Scientists have confirmed that walking refreshes, clears the brain, increases creative potential and even prolongs life. A 12-year study found that people over the age of 65 who walked 15 minutes a day had a 22 percent lower death rate.

Read more books. Despite the living conditions, each of us has the opportunity to read books, which is a hobby of Bill Gates, one of the richest people in the world. It is an economical and very effective way to increase our knowledge level. Winston Churchill spent several hours a day reading biographical, historical, economic and philosophical books. Theodore Roosevelt read 1 book on busy days and 2-3 books on days off. Mark Cuban reads more than 3 hours a day. Billionaire David Rubenstein reads 6 books a week. Elon Musk read 2 books a week when he was young. This list can be continued indefinitely. Reading improves memory, increases empathy and reduces stress, thus helping us achieve our goals.

Find a good conversation partner. The experience of many mature people shows that communication with others helps to look at the situation from a different perspective and even create something completely new. According to writer Joshua Shenka, creative potential develops as a result of interacting with other people. In his book Powers of Two, he talks about duos who have reached great heights through joint efforts. For example, Tolkien and Lewis read drafts of their writings to each other and met every Monday evening. Scientists Francis Crick and James Watson had a lot of communication and had lunch together, and later together with Maurice Wilkinon they determined the structure of DNA. And Theodore Roosevelt had a tennis room where members played tennis together and discussed political issues.

Not being afraid to make mistakes. Everyone makes mistakes, no matter how good they are. They should be considered as an experience that will certainly be useful in the future. Success directly depends on the number of experiments conducted by you. One success "washes away" all your failed attempts. Before Thomas Edison invented the alkaline battery, his more than 50,000 experiments ended in failure. It took 9,000 unsuccessful attempts to create the perfect lamp. Nevertheless, by the end of his life, Edison owned 1,100 patents. It is not necessary to conduct experiments only in practice. Einstein, for example, had them in his mind, which helped him develop his invaluable scientific theories. In addition to correspondence, the diaries of Thomas Edison and Leonardo da Vinci also contain mental cards and various drawings.

Experiences help develop useful skills. Producer and screenwriter Shonda Rhimes decided to get rid of her overwork and obvious introversion and began to admit what she was afraid of before. This experience is called "The year to say yes to everything".

The correct distribution of time is very important. Because how you allocate your time determines a lot of things. Including: Who are we? Who will we be? What do we achieve in life? How do we relate to others? What do we value more than anything else? Here are the principles that guide how we spend each day, hour, and moment:

- Carpe Diem;
- Choosing the best of the best;
- Always trying to do the right thing;
- To be what he wants.

Carpe Diem. Ask yourself, "What am I doing right now?" and enjoy the moment as much as possible. Meet your friends, don't be distracted by anything else. Communicate with them, have fun. If you are doing the dishes, just focus on that and don't think about anything else. Understanding what you are doing is not enough. Unnecessary, complete dedication to training is also a waste of time, as is constant distraction.

Don't forget what you are doing right now. If you find yourself drifting out of the moment, stop yourself. If you decide to spend time with friends or family, leave your phone in the car or somewhere else where you won't be distracted, and enjoy the moment.

Choosing the best of the best. In any situation, "Can I spend my time better than this?" ask a question. If you're not 100 percent sure of what you're doing, don't. Instead, you can engage in a healthy activity. You can do many useful things right now: go to the gym, read a book, hang out with friends, go to a restaurant or cafe for a family meal. But everyone chooses which of them is the best.

Try to get rid of the things that prevent you from devoting your life to "The Best". Take control of how much time you spend on this exercise.

Always trying to do the right thing. Each situation will have at least two different ways to handle it. For example, do you get up immediately when the alarm goes off in the morning, or do you press the button and continue to sleep? Do you hear your interlocutor, or do you mostly talk yourself? Do you praise or criticize your partner? Every situation is a crossroads. We always have to choose which way to go. It's even harder to get it right. However, you have the

opportunity to follow the right path. As time goes by, you will enjoy your life and the fruits of your labor.

To be what he wants. How do you want to be tomorrow? What about in five, ten, twenty years? What about when you're eighty? Once you make a decision about how you see yourself in the future, start moving in that direction. Otherwise, you cannot be the person you want to be. Only two percent of humanity can fully imagine their life, keeping in mind who they will be at the end of their lives. Whatever your views and values are, act on them and never stop.

Proper time management leads to lower stress levels and increased work efficiency and life satisfaction. Time is distributed by properly planning the daily routine. It is important that you make your daily work plan clear and understandable. Smart people also plan their days off properly. By managing your time properly, you won't risk wasting too much time on useless things. Most of us can call the pace of life calm and steady. It's clear that there is not enough time due to a lot of running around. Stress, aggression, depression, and being a victim of fatigue are caused by improper time management. The easiest way to manage time is to make a plan:

- Daily Plan: Most successful people in life have made these plans a part of their life.
- Writing down plans: If one writes down one's plans, the direction towards one's goal will be clearly visible.
- Make a plan in the evening: if you start every work early in the morning, it will bring blessings to your work.
- Know how to separate the important things: in this case, the main task of "Time management" is to identify. Get rid of things you don't need in your plan. Move towards the main subject.
- Learn to say "no": don't try to do anything that has nothing to do with your plans and try to get away from it.
- Avoid time-wasting activities: Prioritize your work and avoid unnecessary activities. The benefit of this is definitely visible.

Unlike foreign countries, we also need to develop our own "Time management". It is not worth wasting every second of our life for this. If every Uzbek family has their own "Time management", their life will be full of unique moments. Taking into account the time allotted to a person from waking up, he will definitely have enough time in his daily activities for mental, physical work, cultural events, walks, watching TV, reading books and doing his favorite sport.

He can enjoy every activity. For this, people need to wake up from the sleep of indifference. Take small breaks between each task. It is very useful for health. No matter what your job is, give your brain a rest and engage in various interesting activities.

The most effective way to be productive is to manage your time properly. Plan your actions using "Time management". It's very simple. Write down your to-do list for tomorrow . Divide these tasks into 4 groups. These groups can be:

1. Urgent and important
2. Important, but not urgent
3. Urgent, but not very important
4. Inconsequential and non-urgent

We divide the work to be done into these categories and check the status of these works at the end of the day.

You don't have to work 7 days a week. It is appropriate if we work on time, get education and relax with family. Like most people, in 2-3 months, you can go abroad or other regions for a vacation with your family. If not, you can go to a restaurant for lunch or dinner once a week. It's all up to you, you can set goals and plans.

Time management planning. Starting your time management with a plan creates a solid foundation for future habits, increasing your chances of success. For example, plan your week on Sunday.

Going into the work week with a plan helps you focus on your priorities. It also makes it easier to transition from a carefree weekend mindset to a productive Monday morning. Take a few minutes on Sunday and make a plan for your entire week. Increase your chances of success by breaking down your weekly goals into daily tasks. That way, you can see at a glance what you need to do each day. Set yourself up for success by scheduling fewer tasks for Saturdays and other low-energy times. Remember, your energy and creativity levels fluctuate throughout the week. Do creative and demanding tasks on Tuesday and Wednesday. Schedule meetings for the second half of the week, when your team's energy starts to wane . Use Saturday and Sunday to plan for the coming week and relax.

For most people, the first hours of work are the most productive. Surprisingly, you can focus more easily when your brain isn't fully awake. A working brain has less energy to daydream and worry about other tasks. Use this to your advantage and do the most mentally challenging tasks first when you wake up.

Time management - work-life balance. Work and life may seem separate, but what you do in one area of your life has a profound effect on the other. Creating

and sticking to your personal "Time Management" will help you reach great heights and achieve more in your life.

Time management can change the way you work. Track time, get and share meaningful reports, and never wonder where your day went. Time management work-life balance. Work and life may seem separate, but what you do in one area of your life has a profound effect on the other. Following healthy lifestyle habits will help you achieve more when you get to work.

CONCLUSION:

To achieve the desired goals, it is necessary to allocate time correctly. If you spend it on things that will benefit you in the future, you will be more likely to succeed. Being able to properly distribute and manage your own energy will create a foundation for your success in the near future, achieving new milestones, and conquering great heights!

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